

Volumetric stability of biphasic hap/ β -tcp/collagen implants in malar augmentation: A CBCT-Based case series after orthognathic surgery

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Evaluate volumetric stability and symmetry of Biphasic Hydroxyapatite (HAp)/ β -Tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP)/collagen (BCP-collagen) implants in malar augmentation post-orthognathic surgery over one year using Cone-Beam-CT (CBCT) and explore influencing factors.

Methods: Retrospective case-series analysis of 45 patients (38 females) who underwent bimaxillary orthognathic surgery with malar augmentation using BCP-collagen implants. CBCT scans were taken at 1 week, 4 months, and 12 months post-surgery. Regression analysis explored potential factors influencing volume loss, including age and sex ($p < 0.05$).

Results: Median patient-age was 26 years (IQR: 22–32). One week postoperatively, median implant-volume was 1356.70 mm^3 (SD = 5888.53). By four-months, it decreased to 985.46 mm^3 (SD = 4352.47), a 25.4 % reduction ($p < 0.001$). Afterwards, a 1.3 % volume decrease ($p = 0.42$). Volume loss varied between 35.1 and 14.7 %. Asymmetry $>7\%$ was observed in 17.7 % of patients. No significant differences in volume loss were found between sexes ($p = 0.6$) or age groups ($p > 0.9$). Regression showed no significant associations with age ($\beta = 0.02$, 95 %CI: $-0.48, 0.53$, $p > 0.9$) or sex ($\beta = 11$, 95 %CI: $-30, 52$, $p = 0.6$).

Conclusion: BCP-collagen implants exhibit early volume loss but stabilise long-term. High variability and asymmetry in volumetric changes challenge standard overcorrection strategies, emphasising the need for early monitoring. CBCT enables precise volumetric assessment and may improve surgical decision-making.

1. Introduction

Symmetrical and defined cheekbones contribute significantly to facial aesthetics, and a deficient malar zone can adversely affect a patient's appearance. Midfacial flatness or sagging is often associated with ageing and negative facial vectors, commonly observed in patients undergoing bimaxillary orthognathic surgeries (Robiony et al., 1998). Despite advancements in surgical techniques, addressing malar deficiencies remains challenging, particularly when untreated during LeFort I osteotomies, often resulting in suboptimal aesthetic and functional outcomes (Fattahi, 2007).

Techniques for malar augmentation include autologous fat grafting, dermal fillers, and a variety of alloplastic materials such as porous

polyethylene (Medpor), silicone, and polyetheretherketone (PEEK) (Rojas et al., 2018). While soft tissue fillers offer minimally invasive correction, they may require repeated treatments (Rojas et al., 2018). Alloplastic implants provide a stable volume but carry risks including infection, migration, or a foreign body reaction (French et al., 2020; Oliver et al., 2019). In contrast, bioactive materials such as biphasic HAp/ β -TCP composites combine osteoconductivity with gradual resorption and integration (Rh Owen et al., 2018), offering a middle ground between permanence and adaptability (Grybauskas et al., 2016).

Porous hydroxyapatite (HAp) granules are widely used for facial augmentation due to their biocompatibility, osteoconductivity, and low long-term resorption (Dutta et al., 2015; Mendelson et al., 2010). However, their granular nature complicates achieving stable fixation.

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Adding microfibrillar collagen improves implant cohesiveness and handling but increases postoperative volume loss, demanding higher initial overcorrection to achieve stable outcomes (Byrd et al., 1993; Grybauskas et al., 2015; Moreira-Gonzalez et al., 2003). Current recommendations suggest overcorrection by 20 % to offset volume loss (Grybauskas et al., 2015; Mendelson et al., 2010; Moreira-Gonzalez et al., 2003). While studies emphasise biocompatibility and general volume retention of biphasic calcium phosphate (BCP) and collagen composites, gaps persist in understanding their predictability, symmetry, and volumetric changes (Grybauskas et al., 2015; Motta et al., 2011).

Previous studies have shown that biphasic calcium phosphate materials exhibit early volume loss, likely attributable to the resorption of the β -Tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP) component and physical compaction of the granules during early healing, followed by stable long-term retention of the hydroxyapatite (HA) phase. (Grybauskas et al., 2015). A 20 % average volumetric change typically occurs within the first four months post-surgery, with negligible changes afterwards (Gerbino et al., 2021; Grybauskas et al., 2015). However, recent studies evaluating malar augmentation in orthognathic surgery using zygomatic osteotomy have highlighted significant variability in volumetric and geometric outcomes in soft tissue and bony projection (Gerbino et al., 2021). These findings emphasise the need to investigate variability rather than relying solely on average stability metrics for malar augmentation. Unresolved issues include the variability in volumetric changes over time, symmetry across bilateral malar regions, and the influence of patient-specific factors such as soft tissue thickness, bone density, and healing capacity on implant outcomes (Mendelson et al., 2010). Addressing these gaps necessitates using validated and reproducible imaging methods, such as cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT), which allows for precise assessment of volumetric changes and facilitates objective evaluation of implant behaviour over time (Andriola et al., 2022). This study investigated the variability in volumetric stability and symmetry of biphasic Hydroxyapatite (HAP)/ β -Tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP)/collagen (BCP-collagen) implants over one year period after orthognathic surgery, using CBCT imaging—a validated method for precise volumetric assessment—to quantify changes and explore potential influencing factors.

2. Methods

This case series is reported following the CARE (Case Report) guidelines (Gagnier et al., 2014).

2.1. Patient information

2.1.1. De-identified patient information

This study included 45 patients who underwent bimaxillary orthognathic surgery with malar augmentation between 2015 and 2019 and were treated at S'OS clinic, Vilnius, Lithuania. A total of 50 patients were initially considered, but one was excluded due to unilateral augmentation, as these cases were excluded to ensure a valid analysis of bilateral symmetry. Four patients were excluded for insufficient postoperative imaging. Data from 90 malar zones were analysed, and patient anonymity was maintained following institutional ethics committee guidelines of the Committee of Ethics of the Riga Stradiņš University (Nr 3/August 18, 2016).

2.1.2. Eligibility criteria

Eligibility was based on the following patient criteria: (1) underwent bilateral malar augmentation during bimaxillary orthognathic surgery, (2) had complete CBCT imaging available at all designated time points, and (3) had no history of prior malar augmentation. Patients were excluded if they: (1) had systemic diseases known to affect bone metabolism (e.g., diabetes mellitus, autoimmune disorders), (2) were current smokers, (3) were undergoing long-term treatment with corticosteroids

or bisphosphonates, or (4) had inadequate postoperative imaging data.

2.1.3. Primary concerns and symptoms

Patients were referred for consultation due to aesthetic concerns or by orthodontists for functional or aesthetic evaluation.

2.1.4. Medical, family, and psychosocial history

No significant medical, familial, or psychosocial history was noted.

2.1.5. Relevant past interventions and outcomes

All patients had received prior orthodontic treatment, and none had undergone malar augmentation procedures. Before surgery, baseline CBCT scans were obtained for all patients.

2.2. Clinical findings

2.2.1. Significant physical examination (PE) and important clinical findings

All patients underwent standard preoperative evaluation, including consultation with an anesthesiologist and routine preoperative preparation. Clinical examination revealed Class II or III malocclusions as the primary functional concern.

2.3. Timeline

All the patients underwent orthodontic treatment before surgery as part of their treatment plan for dentofacial correction. CBCT scans were obtained one week before surgery to use for virtual surgical planning and also to establish baseline volumetric measurements of the midface region. During the surgical phase, all patients underwent bimaxillary orthognathic surgery, including LeFort I osteotomy, with simultaneous malar augmentation. As described previously by (Grybauskas et al., 2015). BCP/collagen implants were prepared intraoperatively and inserted into subperiosteal pockets in the malar region (Grybauskas et al., 2015). Postoperative follow-up included CBCT scans conducted at three time points: 1 week, 4 months, and 12 months after surgery. This schedule follows the S'OS clinic protocol, similar to described protocols to track superimpositions (Andriola et al., 2022). These time points were selected to capture early surgical outcomes, bone healing, and long-term volumetric stability (Grybauskas et al., 2015). All CBCT scans were performed using iCAT machine (Imaging Science International, Hatfield, PA) with a 16 × 22 cm field of view and a voxel size of 0.3 mm. Patients also attended regular clinical visits during this period for assessment and monitoring of healing and potential complications.

2.4. Diagnostic assessment

2.4.1. Diagnostic testing

The inclusion criteria required patients to undergo complete CBCT imaging at four time points: one week preoperatively, one week postoperatively, four months postoperatively, and twelve months postoperatively. A total of 50 patients were initially assessed; however, one was excluded due to unilateral augmentation and four were excluded because of incomplete imaging examination. Data from 90 malar zones of 45 patients were included in the final analysis.

2.4.2. Diagnostic challenges

No specific diagnostic challenges were encountered during the study.

2.4.3. Diagnosis

All patients in the study presented with skeletal Class II or Class III malocclusions.

2.4.4. Prognosis

Based on previous studies, an average 20 % volumetric decrease is expected following malar augmentation with BCP/collagen implants

(Grybauskas et al., 2015).

2.5. Therapeutic intervention

2.5.1. Types of therapeutic intervention

Malar augmentation was performed simultaneously with bimaxillary orthognathic surgery, often in combination with additional procedures such as mentoplasty. During the LeFort I osteotomy, subperiosteal pockets were created in the malar regions. Pre-prepared biphasic HAp/ β -TCP/collagen (BCP/collagen) implants were shaped intraoperatively, inserted into these pockets, and secured using one osteosynthesis screw and a single ring from the osteosynthesis plate on each side, following the technique described by Grybauskas et al. (2015, 2016). The volume of material inserted per malar zone was not standardized, as it was tailored to the patient's anatomical structure and aesthetic goals based on the surgeon's clinical judgment. This variability in implant volume was acknowledged as a limitation affecting reproducibility in the study.

2.5.2. Administration of therapeutic intervention (dosage, strength, duration)

The implants were prepared intraoperatively according to established protocols (Byrd et al., 1993; Grybauskas et al., 2015). HAp/ β -TCP granules, were hydrated with sterile water and mixed with Avitene™ Microfibrillar Collagen Hemostat Flour. Excess moisture was removed manually, and the material was divided into blocks. These blocks were shaped into cones using sterile instruments and dried under a heating lamp until they solidified. All procedures were performed by a single oral and maxillofacial surgeon with over 20 years of experience.

2.5.3. Changes in therapeutic intervention

No modifications were made to the therapeutic intervention protocol.

2.6. Follow up

2.6.1. Clinician and patient-assessed outcomes

All patients underwent standardized CBCT imaging protocols during follow-up. CBCT scans were imported into Slicer 3D software (<http://www.slicer.org>) in DICOM format (Fedorov et al., 2012), with the pre-surgical scan as the baseline. CBCT datasets were superimposed using voxel-based registration with the cranial base as the stable reference. The midface region was segmented with a threshold of 200 grey-scale units, followed by manual adjustments to refine the segmentation and fill gaps. Surface models were generated, and Boolean subtractions were performed to calculate volumetric changes between time points (Fig. 1).

Three volumetric models were created for analysis.

- M1: Representing volume gained immediately after surgery.
- M2: Representing volume lost during the first four months post-surgery.
- M3: Representing volume lost between 4 and 12 months post-surgery.

The left and right malar regions were separated for each model to generate individual volumetric measurements. These values were recorded for further analysis.

All asymmetry measurements were derived from these CBCT-based volumetric assessments. The asymmetry threshold was defined as a

Fig. 1. Shows the relative change in implant volume for each patient at one week, four months, and twelve months post-operation.

A- preoperative volume (green) with T1 volume increase (beige) superimposed

B- right side malar area superimposition of T0, T1, T2, T3; C- amount of volume decrease between T1 and T2 (translucent blue) and amount of volume decrease between T2 and T3 (orange). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

>7 % volumetric difference between the left and right malar regions. This value exceeds the minimal variability reported for facial landmarks (4–6 %) (Ferrario et al., 2001) and approximates the perceptual threshold of 3 mm required for visible facial asymmetry (Chu et al., 2011).

2.6.2. Follow-up diagnostic and other test results

Only patients with complete follow-up CBCT imaging were included, resulting in a final dataset of 90 malar zones from 45 patients. Volumetric data were extracted from DICOM files, tabulated, and exported for statistical analysis. All data have been deposited in the Zenodo repository (Lauskis et al., 2024). Statistical analyses evaluated volumetric changes over time, using paired t-tests to compare measurements at each postoperative time point against baseline values. Relative changes in volume over time were calculated as percentages of baseline values. Three volumetric models (M1, M2, M3) were analysed to assess changes at different postoperative stages. Exploratory data analysis (EDA) and descriptive statistics summarised patient demographics and volumetric measurements at 1 week, 4 months, and 12 months post-surgery. Subgroup analyses by age and sex were conducted using linear regression models to evaluate their potential influence on volumetric outcomes. A significance level of 5 % was applied.

2.6.3. Intervention adherence and tolerability

Patient adherence was inferred from attendance at scheduled follow-up visits and compliance with postoperative recovery timelines. All patients resumed normal activities within 2–4 weeks following surgery, consistent with standard recovery for orthognathic procedures. No additional structured assessments of adherence were performed, but the absence of complications or interruptions in follow-up suggests good compliance overall.

2.6.4. Adverse and unanticipated events

Adverse events were consistent with those commonly associated with orthognathic surgery and included postoperative swelling and transient paresthesia in the malar and midface regions (Kim, 2017). No severe complications or unanticipated events were reported.

2.6.5. Informed consent

All patients provided informed consent following clinic protocols, including permitting the use of de-identified clinical data for research and dissemination purposes.

3. Results

3.1. Demographic variables

The study included 45 participants (38 females) who underwent orthognathic surgery with BCP/collagen implants for malar augmentation. The median age of the participants was 26 year-old, with an interquartile range (IQR) of 22–32 (Table 1).

3.2. Absolute changes in volume over time

Analysis of absolute volumetric changes showed a consistent decrease from the initial postoperative period (1 week) to the final

follow-up at 12 months. The median implant volume at 1 week post-operatively served as the baseline for comparison. By 4 months, the median implant volume decreased from 1356.70 mm³ (SD: 5888.53) to 985.46 mm³ (SD: 4352.47), with minimal change by 12 months, stabilising at 991.59 mm³ (SD: 4274.02). Volumetric analysis at 1 week, 4 months, and 12 months post-surgery demonstrated a progressive reduction in variability, with implant volumes stabilising by the final follow-up (Fig. 2).

At 1 week postoperatively, implant volumes varied widely (3775.51 mm³–11358.10 mm³). This variability decreased by 4 months (3062.08 mm³–4352.47 mm³) and remained consistent at 12 months (2991.13 mm³–4274.02 mm³).

3.3. Relative changes in volume over time

Relative changes were calculated as percentages based on the formula: [(Final Volume - Initial Volume)/Initial Volume] × 100. The baseline was set at 100 % one-week post-operation. By four months, the mean relative change dropped to 74.6 %, with a standard deviation of 8.3 and a standard error of 1.2, resulting in a 95 % confidence interval from 72.1 % to 77 %. At 12 months, the mean relative change dropped to 73.3 %, with a standard deviation of 9.1 and a standard error of 1.4, resulting in a 95 % confidence interval from 70.6 % to 75.9 %. Fig. 3 presents the individual patient-level changes in relative volume over time, illustrating inter-patient variability in volume retention.

3.3.1. Comparison of Left and Right Malar Regions Over Time

The subanalysis comparing the left and right malar regions showed no significant asymmetry over time (Fig. 4).

3.4. Demographic influence on volumetric changes

Regression analysis revealed no significant associations between age, sex, and relative volumetric changes. Table 2 shows that age has a beta coefficient of 0.02 with a 95 % confidence interval from -0.48 to 0.53 and a p-value greater than 0.9. Regression analysis showed a beta of 11 for males (95 % CI: -30 to 52, p = 0.6). The interaction term between age and sex had a beta of -0.90 with a confidence interval of -2.4 to 0.55 and a p-value = 0.2.

4. Discussion

This study investigated the volumetric stability and symmetry of BCP/collagen implants used in malar augmentation over a one-year follow-up. Consistent with previous studies, most volume loss occurred within the first four months, with an average reduction of 25.4 % of the initial implant volume (Grybauskas et al., 2015; Mendelson et al., 2010). Between four and twelve months, the additional reduction was 1.3 %.

Malar augmentation techniques differ in material, placement, and durability. Fat grafting is biocompatible and minimally invasive but has unpredictable resorption and often needs repeat procedures (Guijarro-Martínez et al., 2011). Dermal fillers allow non-surgical correction but require reinjection and can cause vascular occlusion, nodules, or granulomas (Oranges et al., 2021). Alloplastic implants such as silicone, Medpor, and PEEK provide structural support but carry risks of infection, displacement, and foreign body reactions, which may lead to revision surgery (Oliver et al., 2019). BCP/collagen implants promote bone integration through osteoconduction but lose volume early and do not provide structural rigidity, making planned overcorrection necessary (Grybauskas et al., 2015). Selection should reflect patient anatomy, treatment goals, and tolerance for revision. The present study results confirm that BCP/collagen implants reach volumetric stability after the initial compaction and resorption phase.

However, the study identified considerable variability in patient volumetric changes, contrasting with the relatively predictable trends

Table 1
Demographic characteristics of study participants.

Characteristic	N = 45 ¹
Age	26.0 (22.0, 32.0)
Sex	
F	38 (84 %)
M	7 (16 %)
1 Median (IQR); n (%)	

Fig. 2. Violin plot of absolute change in volume by time.

Fig. 3. Individual patient relative volume changes over time.

previously reported in the literature (Grybauskas et al., 2015; Mendelson et al., 2010). Notably, while most patients exhibited volume loss consistent with the anticipated 15–20 % overcorrection, some experienced reductions exceeding 35 %, while others demonstrated losses of less than 15 %. This heterogeneity highlights that the recommendation

of applying a uniform overcorrection may not adequately address individual patient responses. Additionally, asymmetry was observed in 17.7 % of cases, with differences in volume loss between the left and right malar zones exceeding 7 %. Achieving symmetry is critical in facial aesthetics, and these findings highlight the need for more refined

Fig. 4. Comparison of left and right malar regions over time: No significant asymmetry observed.

Table 2

Exploratory regression analysis of the difference in relative change by age and sex.

Characteristic	Beta	95 % CI ¹	p-value
Age	0.02	-0.48, 0.53	>0.9
Sex			
F	-	-	
M	11	-30, 52	0.6
Age * Sex			
Age * M	-0.90	-2.4, 0.55	0.2

1 CI = Confidence Interval

surgical planning and execution to address the variability in both volumetric changes and bilateral outcomes.

This study has some limitations to consider when interpreting the findings. First, as a retrospective analysis, implant volumes could not be measured pre-insertion; the first postoperative CBCT scan within one week served as the baseline, excluding immediate post-surgery compaction and migration. On the other hand, CBCT provides a precise volumetric evaluation, ensuring an accurate assessment of changes over time. Second, the one-year follow-up focuses on early volume loss, which accounts for most changes, as previous studies report minimal additional loss beyond this period (Grybauskas et al., 2015; Mendelson et al., 2010). We believe further follow-up would not reveal significant changes in implant volume. Third, a single experienced surgeon performed all procedures. The single-surgeon design ensured standardisation of the technique and cost efficiency, but it also limited the generalizability of the findings, as the results may reflect the specific skill of the surgeon (Lejniaks et al., 2024; Semenkovich et al., 2019). However, the primary focus of this study was the variability in volumetric changes after surgery. Given that such variability was observed even with an experienced surgeon, it is reasonable to extrapolate that it would also occur with other surgeons, regardless of their experience level.

The findings of this study align with previous research on biphasic HAp/ β -TCP implants, particularly regarding the pattern of early volume loss followed by long-term stability. Grybauskas et al. reported a total

volume loss of 21.65 % over 24 months, with 20.98 % occurring within the first 12 months (Grybauskas et al., 2015; Mendelson et al., 2010). This study observed a higher average volume loss of 26.7 % over one year, with 25.4 % occurring in the first four months. This finding reinforces that the most significant reduction occurs within the early postoperative period. Beyond this initial phase, changes were negligible, supporting the establishment of volumetric stability within the first year.

While Grybauskas et al. (2015) emphasised the predictability of implant behaviour after the compaction phase, our findings challenge this assumption by highlighting significant inter-patient variability. Unlike previous studies that primarily reported average trends, we documented a wide range of volumetric changes, with some patients experiencing reductions exceeding 35 % while others showed losses below 15 %. This suggests that while the overall trends align with prior research, the magnitude of individual variation has been underreported.

This study aimed to quantify individual variability rather than develop predictive models based on demographic characteristics. While previous research has focused on average volume retention, our findings revealed high inter-patient variability despite applying a standard 20 % overcorrection protocol derived from earlier work (Grybauskas et al., 2015). We explored associations with age and sex, but these variables showed no significant influence on volume loss. As a result, individual outcomes remain difficult to anticipate using demographic data alone. Most volume reduction occurred within the first four months, suggesting that increased follow-up during this period may help identify and address excessive resorption or asymmetry early.

Our findings also contrast with those of Mendelson et al. who reported near-complete stability of hydroxyapatite implants from three months onward (Mendelson et al., 2010). While pure hydroxyapatite is known for its long-term volume retention due to minimal resorption, it lacks the remodeling capacity provided by β -TCP, which supports gradual replacement by host bone (Mangano et al., 2015). In this study, a biphasic HAp/ β -TCP composite was selected to promote osteoconduction while allowing for partial resorption and integration into the native bone. This property is considered beneficial in orthognathic surgery cases, where the implant is expected to conform to dynamic bone healing and remodeling. Additionally, microfibrillar collagen was

added to the composite to improve intraoperative handling and reduce granule migration. This combination allowed the material to be molded and stabilized within the subperiosteal pocket (Byrd et al., 1993; Grybauskas et al., 2016). Although biphasic materials exhibit more early resorption than pure hydroxyapatite, their improved adaptability and potential for biological integration made them suitable for the present surgical indication. Mendelson's study did not include early postoperative volumetric assessments, thus omitting initial compaction effects. This makes comparisons with our findings difficult. Their sample included only female patients, while ours included both sexes. Although our analysis showed no significant differences in volume loss by sex ($p = 0.6$), sex-based differences in bone density and soft tissue response are well documented and could influence outcomes in other study designs. Another methodological difference is imaging: Mendelson et al. used conventional CT with 0.5–1 mm slice thickness, while we used CBCT with 0.075–0.4 mm slices (Icen et al., 2020), allowing finer resolution of early volume changes.

The observed variability raises questions about the roles of implant composition, patient-specific anatomical factors, and surgical technique. Unlike alloplastic implants, such as silicone or Medpor, which maintain their volume but are associated with complications like migration and foreign body reactions (Alonso-Rodriguez et al., 2015; French et al., 2020; Oliver et al., 2019), BCP/collagen implants integrate with host tissue and undergo controlled resorption. However, the extent of this process appears to vary considerably among patients, warranting further investigation into factors influencing implant behaviour. Other studies have also not specifically measured the influence of soft tissue thickness or bone density on volumetric variability, leaving their precise impact an open question for future research.

Finally, this study is the first to document asymmetry in volumetric changes with biphasic calcium phosphate implants. While previous studies have primarily focused on overall volume loss, we found that 17.7 % of patients exhibited a volume reduction difference of more than 7 % between the malar zones. This has direct clinical relevance, as asymmetries of 3 mm or more can significantly impact facial aesthetics (Chu et al., 2011; Chu et al., 2011).

The unpredictability of volume loss observed in this study is likely influenced by multiple interrelated factors. Collagen, which initially provides cohesiveness to the implant, gradually resorbs, contributing to early volumetric reduction. Additionally, the granular structure of biphasic HAp/ β -TCP implants enables compaction under physiological loads, further reducing volume in the early postoperative period. The resorption characteristics of β -TCP, designed to be osteoconductive, also introduce an additional source of variation, as its degradation rate may differ among patients due to individual biological responses. Finally, potential material migration may contribute to unpredictable volume changes due to improper subperiosteal pocket preparation or intraoperative manual shaping. While these factors have been recognised in previous research (Grybauskas et al., 2015; Mendelson et al., 2010), their impact remains difficult to quantify.

The variability in volumetric changes challenges the standard 15–20 % overcorrection guideline (Grybauskas et al., 2015; Mendelson et al., 2010), as some patients experienced losses exceeding 35 % while others had reductions below 15 %. This highlights the necessity of individualised overcorrection strategies tailored to each patient's expected resorption pattern. Additionally, this study identified a 17.7 % asymmetry rate in volume loss, emphasising the importance of precise implant positioning and even compaction to minimise aesthetic discrepancies. Since the most significant volume loss occurs within the first four months, close postoperative monitoring is essential to detect and address excessive resorption and emerging asymmetries early, optimising long-term outcomes.

Also, since CBCT's higher resolution improves volumetric assessment (Icen et al., 2020), integrating high-resolution CBCT into follow-ups may enhance surgical decision-making. Furthermore, CBCT volumetric assessments should utilise a small field of view to enable higher-resolution

imaging with smaller voxel sizes, improving sensitivity to subtle volumetric changes (van Leeuwen et al., 2022) to track implant behaviour and refine overcorrection strategies.

5. Conclusion

This study confirms that biphasic BCP/collagen implants undergo the most significant volume loss (25.4 %) within the first four months, followed by minimal changes up to one year. However, the high patient variability challenges the predictability of standard overcorrection strategies. While a 15–20 % overcorrection may suffice for some, others require individualised adjustments. The 17.7 % asymmetry rate highlights the need for close monitoring immediately after surgery, particularly during the first four months, when 95 % of the total volume loss occurred based on our results. High-resolution CBCT with a small field of view (van Leeuwen et al., 2022) can enhance volumetric assessment and surgical planning. Future research should explore patient-specific factors influencing variability and consider customised 3D-printed implants to improve predictability and implant stability.

Authors contributions

ML, GS, and SG contributed to the conception and design of the study. SG, ML, SEU, and OR with data acquisition and interpretation performed all statistical analyses; SEU and ML drafted the manuscript; and ML, GS, OR, SEU, and SG critically revised the manuscript. All authors gave their final approval and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Data availability statement

The dataset supporting this study's findings is available in the Zenodo repository with the identifier <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13200856>.

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